

The Potential Adverse Health Effects of Residents Near Hazardous Municipal Solid Waste Dump Site - At Jawahar Nagar- Hyderabad

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Abstract

In this research paper the Survey has been conducted among 45 residents around the main dumping site of the municipal corporation viz Jawahar Nagar. In this survey it was found that 55% of the people are suffering with respiratory and 45% answered that they not suffering from the respiratory diseases. Twenty five percent of the People suffering from Cough, twenty percent with Bronchitis, twenty percent with Asthma, fifteen percent with Sneezing, ten percent with Suffocation and the rest of the people suffering with other diseases. All the sample householders had different kinds of eye diseases. It was noted that 20% of households had reddening of eye, 65% of households had tearing of eye, 5% of the householders suffered from difficulty in vision and 10% of households were affected by conjunctivitis. The high occurrence of eye diseases in the area might be due to recurrence of fire and gas emissions from the dumping site. During the survey, it was observed that the people around the dump site was suffering from various water borne diseases such as Cholera, Dysentery, Typhoid, Jaundice, Diarrhea etc. Nearly 25% of the people suffering from cholera, 25% from Diarrhea, 20% from Jaundice, 15% from typhoid, 10% from Dysentery etc. It was found that 25% had Cholera, 20% had Jaundice; 25% had Diarrhea; 10% had Dysentery; 15% had Typhoid and 5% had other Diseases.

Keywords: Municipal Solid Waste (MSW), Health Problems, Dump Site , Jawahar Nagar, Diseases .

1. Introduction

The Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) management significantly contributes to the emissions of green house gases into the atmosphere and therefore management of this waste is vital for a healthy environment. Management of MSW has become a significant environmental problem especially in metropolitan cities. Pollution and health risks create by improper solid waste management are an important issue that is a cause of major worry to any government, especially in developing countries. Lack of awareness, infrastructure, planning and public awareness is surely the main culprits in this regard. No wonder waste management has become a herculean task for any metropolis. This study analyzes and compares the findings of the study of the characterization and the generation and disposal of domestic solid waste.(U.S. Climate Action Report 2010) Over the last few decades in India, there has been a significant increase in the generation of municipal solid wastes. The main reasons are population explosion, unplanned urbanization, industrialization etc. The daily per capita generation of solid waste ranges from about 100 to 500 g in large towns. The recyclable content of waste ranges from 13 to 20%. A study conducted by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) on management of municipal solid waste in the country estimates that waste generation from the present 48 million tones is expected to increase to 300 million tones per year by the year 2047 (490g per capita to 945 g per capita). The estimated requirement of land disposal would be 169.6 sq.km in 2047 as against 20.2 sq.km in 1997 (Municipal Solid Waste Management in Asia Report 2004)

MSW disposed as land dump is likely to consist of non - hazardous and hazardous materials. It is also a mixture of compost able and combustible materials. MSW as mixed waste undergoes decay and decay composition on the one hand and catches fire on the other hand. The former produces land and water pollution and the latter produces air pollution. Further MSW offers raw materials for recycling and therefore, waste pickers make visits to the site but they are automatically exposed to health problems. Land dumps are many a time located not far away from human habitation that local residents are also directly or indirectly affected by serious health hazards, because they who lived in the neighborhood, especially the poor, trespassed into the site for picking recyclables and those who kept away from the site are indirectly affected by the air and water pollution. The effects produced may be acute or chronic. Only the immediate or sudden effects catch attention and the others get identified perhaps after several decades of unnoticed damage. Notably leachate flow from the dumpsite and fire at the site are common. So MSW is a potential threat to the health of all people in general and particularly to those who live around the dumping sites. Therefore, a survey was conducted to understand the health problems of people around the main dumping site namely Jawahar Nagar. The objective of the survey was to get an overall picture of health problems faced by them. The sight and smell of garbage, heaped one over the other like hillocks, just overwhelms us. The

Jawaharnagar dumping yard in the city outskirts, in which over 3,800 tonnes of garbage is dumped on a daily basis, continues to be mired with a plethora of problems. Children of the near dump site are falling sick regularly. The smoke from the garbage emits toxic gases and is hazardous for families; The situation for those dwelling very close to the dump yard is far more serious. Families living in Rajiv Gruha Kalpa Apartments near the Jawahamagar dumping yard and the colonies of Jawahamagar, Ahmedguda, Nagaram, Ambedkar Nagar, Hardaspalli and several villages en route to the dump yard have been complaining of ground-water, air and noise pollution besides having to live with the stink of garbage. The local people near by the dump site depended on water tankers because the ground water is polluted. A sound solid waste management system to scientifically treat the garbage still eludes it. There is no proper road connectivity to this dumping yard, where 600 trucks laden with garbage visit on a daily basis. Nearby colony residents frequently complain of ailments, repulsive smell and the nuisance of the moving trucks in their colony roads (Syamala Devi Phd Thesis 2013). While ground water is getting polluted due to Jawahamagar garbage dump, the Greater Hyderabad Municipal Corporation (GHMC) is facing fresh trouble over pollution of lakes in the surrounding areas due to leachate (a solution resulting from leaching, as of soluble constituents from soil, landfill, etc., by downward percolating ground water) of Jawahamagar. Villagers of Cheriyal near Jawahamagar have been demanding that water from Pedda Chervu lake be drained out, while villagers of surrounding villages said water should not enter their lakes and tanks. The GHMC has been dumping about 3,800 metric tonnes (MTs) of garbage daily in the 750-acre dump yard located about 35 kms from the city for the past few years. The objective of the survey was to get on overall picture of the health problems faced by them.

2.Methodology

2.1 Study Area:

An Integrated Municipal Solid Waste Management Scheme is proposed at the existing Jawaharnagar Dump Site, Dommaiguda Village, Keesara Mandal, Ranga Reddy District of Andhra Pradesh (A.P). The area of the proposed for the facility is around 351 acres (142 Hectares). The site is 35 km away from Hyderabad city, 10.5 km away from the state Highway connecting Hyderabad- Nagpur in West direction from the boundary of the project site. The map showing general location of the site with respect to India and A.P and the 10 km radius topographical map around the proposed project and the site layout map of the proposed project was given in Figure 1. Longitude & latitudes of jawahar nagar was +17° 30' 14.18", +78° 34' 4.94" .

Figure 1: Location of the site

2.2 Method

MSW is a potential threat to the health of all people in general and particularly to those who lived around the dumping site. So a survey was conducted to understand the problems of people around the main dumping site (Jawahar Nagar). The objective of the survey was to get an overall picture of the health problems faced by them. The study was conducted during May - June 2009. The data were collected through a structured interview schedule. The researcher personally met 45 respondents who were residing around the site.

3.(A) Results:

Furnished below are the data obtained from the survey conducted among 45 residents around the main dumping site of the corporation viz Jawahar Nagar.

1. Distance of Households from the Dumping Site:

In the survey we observed that 15% of the families had been staying at a close distance of <50 meters from the dumping site. Only 55% of the respondents were staying at distance between 50 - 100 meters from the dumping site; 25% were staying at distance between 100 - 200 meters; 5% were staying at distance more than 200 meters.

Response of People Near Dump Site Fig1: Distance of Households from the Dumping Site

2. Period of Stay around the Dumping Site:

During the study it was revealed that majority (60%) of the respondents has been staying at their present residences for 5-10 years; 15% for 1- 5 years; 14% for 10 - 15 years; 6% for above 15 years and 5% for less than 1 year.

Fig2: Period of Stay around the Dumping Site

3. Dumping Time of MSW:

About 65% of the respondents replied that dumping was done mainly in the forenoon and; 15% preferred to dump in the after noon; 15% preferred to dump in the night and 5% preferred to dump the waste round the clock.

Fig 3: Dumping Time of MSW

4. Unauthorized Persons at the Dumping Site:

Some times unauthorized persons may enter into the dump yard. While we asked about the unauthorized persons at dump yard, 85% of the neighboring households reported the presence of unauthorized persons for scavenging at the Jawahar Nagar dumping site.

Fig 4: Unauthorized Persons at the Dumping Site

5. Fire at the Site:

Fires at the dump site are a natural process. The residents often noticed smoke and fire in the dumping site. This was the response of 95% of the respondents.

Fig 5: Fire at the Site

6. Stray Animals:

The respondents cited the presence of stray animals at the main dumping site. The stray animals included dogs, cows, buffaloes and cats, and it can be noted that 98% of respondents found dogs, 87% found cows, 51% found cats and 42% found buffaloes mainly.

Fig 6: Stray Animals

7. Scavenging Birds:

Among scavenging birds, 89% of people found eagle, 84% of people found crow, 47% observed pigeon and 71% noticed crane.

Fig 7: Scavenging Birds

8. Source and Quality of Water:

About 78% of the respondents depended on municipal tankers for drinking water whereas the rest depended on public taps (55%) and common well (45%). About 15% of the respondents found that water in their wells was turbid but 29% found it clear. However, the respondents did not feel any disagreeable taste or odour to water. Seventeen percent of the respondents used boiled water before drinking but the remaining 83% did not do so.

Fig 8: Source of Drinking Water

9. Foul Smell from Dumping Site:

All the respondents were unanimous in staying that Jawahar Nagar dumping site emitted foul smell. About 80% of the respondents stated that foul smell was mostly in the forenoon. There was foul smell in the afternoon and night also as reported by 11% and 9% respondents respectively.

Fig 9: Appearance of Drinking Water

10. Incidence of Water Borne Diseases:

It was found that 25% had Cholera, 20% had Jaundice; 25% had Diarrhea; 10% had Dysentery; 15% had Typhoid and 5% had other Diseases.

Fig 10: Taste and Odour of Water

11. Incidence of Respiratory Diseases:

The majority of the households (55%) had different kinds of respiratory problems. Among these, 25% had Cough; 20% had Bronchitis; 15% Sneezing; 20% Asthma; 10% Suffocation and 10% other diseases.

Fig 11: Boil the Water Before Drinking

12. Incidence of Eye Diseases:

All the sample householders had different kinds of eye diseases. It was noted that 20% of households had reddening of eye, 65% of households had tearing of eye, 5% of the householders suffered from difficulty in vision and 10% of households were affected by conjunctivitis. The high occurrence of eye diseases in the area might be due to recurrence of fire and gas emissions from the dumping site.

Fig 12: Foul Smell from Dumping Site

Fig 12 a). Time of Foul of Foul Smelling

13. Suffering from Water Borne Diseases:

During the survey, it was observed that the people around the dump site was suffering from various water borne diseases such as Cholera, Dysentery, Typhoid, Jaundice, Diarrhea etc. Nearly 25% of the people suffering from cholera, 25% from Diarrhea, 20% from Jaundice, 15% from typhoid, 10% from Dysentery etc.

Fig 13: Impacts of Water Borne Diseases

14. Incidence of Respiratory Problems:

In the survey it was found that 55% of the people are suffering with respiratory and 45% answered that they not suffering from the respiratory diseases. Twenty five percent of the People suffering from Cough, twenty percent with Bronchitis, twenty percent with Asthma, fifteen percent with Sneezing, ten percent with Suffocation and the rest of the people suffering with other diseases.

Fig14: Incidence of Respiratory Problems

Fig 14 a): Incidence of Respiratory Diseases

15. Illness arising from stay around the Dump Yard:

When we asked a question to people around the dump site about the illness, 90% of the people said yes, and the rest of the people said 10% No. These are facing some illness in the form of tearing of eyes (65%), Reddeing of eyes (20%), Difficulty in Vision (5%) and Conjunctives (10%).

Fig15: Illness arising from stay around the Dump Yard

Fig16: Illness arising from stay around the Dump Yard

3.(B) Discussion:

Landfill sites receive MSW consisting of organic, inorganic and hazardous materials. These in course of time turn into pollutants affecting humans through soil, air and

water. People living around dumping sites thus get succumbed to various diseases.

One of the health hazards developed is quite well known to be from landfill gas. Landfill gas consists of naturally occurring methane and carbon dioxide, which is formed from waste decomposition. It has been reported that volatile organic compounds escaping from the landfills were Tetra - Chloroethylene, Try - Chloroethylene, Toulene 1,1,2,2, Trichloroethane, Benzene, Vinyl chloride, Xylene, Ethylbenzene, Methylene Chloride, 1,2, - dichloroethane and Choloroform. These gases could be toxic. Another helath hazard arouse from generation of leachate which infiltrated and contaminated ground waters which in turn produced water borne diseases to consumers. Some of the constituents of hazardous waste were cancerous too. Several medical report of clinical examination carried out among people who lived near landfill sites are known.

A study by the New York State Department of Health reported that women living near solid waste landfills where gas was escaping had a foul fold increased chance of bladder cancer or Leukaemia (State of New York Department of Health, 1980 - 89). US Environmental Protection Agency examined 593 waste sites in 339 US countries and found elevated cancers of the bladder, lung, stomach and Rectum in countries with the highest concentration of waste sites (Griffith 1989).

A 1986 study of children with Illeukemia in Wobum, Massachusetts statistically linked the diseases to drinking water supplies that had been contaminated by a waste site (Brown and Donnelly, 1988). Another study in San Fransisco Region found a 1.5 fold greater chance of birth defects of the heart and circulatory system among newboms whose parents lived near a solid or hazardous waste site (Shaw 1989). Increased incidence of bladder cancer was reported north western Illinois where a landfill had contaminated a municipal water supply with Trichloroethylene (TCE), Tetrachloroethylene (PERC) and other chlorinated solvents (Mallin, 1990). Similarly increased incidence of Leukemia has been reported in a community near a toxic waste dump in North Rhine Westphalia, Germany (Greiser 1991).

The most commonly reported effect of living near a landfill was low birth weight and small size among children. The first careful study of this subject took place at Love Canal near Niagara Falls, New York. Children who had lived at least 75% of their lives near Love - Canal - the notorious toxic chemical dump - had significantly shorter stature than children who lived farther away from the dumpsite (Paigen 1987).

A 1995 study of families living near a large municipal solid waste dump (the Miron Quarry) near Montreal, Quebec found a 20% increased likelihood of birth weight among those most heavily exposed to gases from the landfill (Goldberg, 1995). A study of families living near the Lipari landfills in New Jersey reported low birth weight aming babies bom during 1971 - 1975 when the landfill gas was thought to have leaked the greatest quantity of toxic materials into the local environment (Berry and Bove 1997). A study of people near the BKK landfill in Los Angeles Country, California in 1997 reported significantly reduced birth weight among children bom during the period of heaviest dumping at the site (Kharrazi 1997). A 1990 study of 590 hazardous waste sites in New York state found a 12% increase in birth defects in families living within a mile of a site. A later report in 1997 found a statistically significant 33% increased chance of a birth defect occurring in babies

bom to families living within 3 kilometers (1.9 miles) of any of 21 landfills in 10 European countries (Vrijheid and Dolk 1997).

4. Conclusion

This study examined the health status of households living around the municipal solid waste dump site- at Jawahar nagar in Hyderabad. In the long term, efforts to provide low cost houses situated in a clean environment is a priority that the government must pursue vigorously to enable the poor to live in affordable yet clean environment. To curtail the menace of high rate of rural-urban migration which is an important source of urban congestion and slum, a policy of integrated development whereby the rural sector is developed to provide jobs and social amenities should be made a priority

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References

- [1] Berry, M and F. Bove.(1997). 'Birth Weight Reduction Associated with residence near a hazardous waste landfill'. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 105(8): 856 – 861.
- [2] Goldberg, M.S. (1995). Incidence of Cancer among Persons living Near a Municipal Landfill Site, Montreal Quebec. *Archives of Environmental Health*.50(6): 416 – 424.
- [3] Gresier, (1991). Increased incidence of Leukemia in the vicinity of previous Industrial Waste Dump North – Rhine West Falia, Germany, *American Journal of Epidemiology*. 134(7): 755.
- [4] Griffith, J. (1989). Cancer Mortality in U.S. Countries with Hazardous Waste sites and Ground water Pollution, *archives of Environmental Health*. 4(2): 69 – 74.
- [5] Kharrazi, M. (1997). A Community Based Study of Adverse Pregnancy outcomes near a Large Hazardous Waste Landfill In California. 'Toxicological and Industrial Health'. 13(2): 299 – 310.
- [6] *Municipal Solid Waste Management in Asia Report (2004)* , Asian Institute of Technology.
- [7] Paigen .B (1987), Growth of children living near the hazardous waste site, Love Canal, *Human Biology*, 59(3) : 489-508.
- [8] Shaw, P. (1989), Rapid Population Growth and Environmental Degradation: Ultimate Versus Proximate Factor, *Environmental Conservation*. 199 – 209.

- [9] Syamala Devi. k, Phd Thesis (2013); Solid Waste Management of Greater Hyderabad Municipal Corporation.
- [10] U.S. Climate Action Report (2010) ,Fifth National Communication of the United States of America Under the United Nations Framework on Climate Change.
- [11] Vrijheid and Dolk. (1997). Residence Near Hazardous Waste Landfill Site and Risk of Non – Chromosomal Congenital Malformations Teratology. 56(6): 401.